

ADOBE BLOCK AND HOME CONSTRUCTION RESEARCH IN RWANDA

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ABSTRACT

This paper summarises the results and conclusions from soil and adobe block testing that informed the DRS 484 Adobe Block Specification and Technical Guidelines on Adobe Block Construction in Rwanda, both of which are to be published in 2022. The soil testing concluded that soil classification could be used to determine if soil is capable of making adobe blocks and identified two field tests that could be used to indicate suitable soils: the soil wash test and the snake test. The block testing concluded that cracking is improved by fibres, compressive strength can be determined by the drop test and durability was not improved by improved manufacturing methods. It was also concluded that environmental conditions have a major impact on block performance.

KEYWORDS

Adobe; Earth; Construction; Rwanda; East Africa; Research; Testing; Soil; Block; Brick

INTRODUCTION

In 2019 Rwanda released the latest version of the Rwanda Building Code (RBC) with a particular emphasis on promotion of use of local construction materials, including the use of adobe block, locally known as Rukarakara.

Adobe block construction is very common in Rwanda, where 67% of households live in adobe homes, with a higher percentage in rural areas (National Institute of Statistics of Rwanda, 2020). Adobe is not only affordable and achieves low embodied carbon, but also does not require major infrastructure to construct with - the skills already exist and the materials required are locally available and plentiful. However, whilst adobe construction can be structurally stable and durable, many homes are poorly built and require significant maintenance. For example, in a 2018 survey of 23 masons and 57 customers carried out by EarthEnable across each of Rwanda's four provinces and the City of Kigali, 70% of masons had no formal training, 85% of roofs leaked and 65% residents didn't feel safe.

The effects of climate change are exacerbating the vulnerability of houses in Rwanda, with 23% of households affected by environmental issues including floods, landslides and heavy rains (National Institute of Statistics of Rwanda, 2020). Rwanda is considered a moderately seismic zone but homes in Rwanda, both formal and informal, are generally not built with seismic design considerations. This can have serious negative impacts, as we can see from the May 2021 Rubavu District seismic event following the eruption of the Nyiragongo Volcano in Goma, after which 2,654 homes were in need of repair, reconstruction or relocation (Government of Rwanda, 2021).

To improve rural housing, the Rwanda Housing Authority (RHA) launched the Local Building Materials Think Tank to bring together parties with complementary expertise to contribute to the development of the following documents which can support RHA in regulating the construction of adobe block homes. Parties involved include RHA, Rwanda Standards Board (RSB), Rwanda Polytechnic, EarthEnable, MASS Design Group and Greenpact Africa.

Both documents will be published in 2022.

- DRS 484 Adobe Block Specification
- Technical Guidelines on Adobe Block Construction in Rwanda

DRS 484 Adobe Block Specification details best practices for fabricating adobe blocks, including soil classification, addition of fibres, manufacturing process, curing process and performance criteria. It includes field tests which may be used to indicate soil suitability and block strength in the absence of access to a laboratory.

The Technical Guidelines for Adobe Block Construction in Rwanda also includes details on the block itself, aligning with DRS 484, but in addition provides guidance on the construction of the whole building. It includes site selection, retaining walls, drainage, block fabrication, construction of the foundations, walls, roof, doors, windows and finishes. Rwanda is considered a moderately seismic zone, and the earthquake hazard level varies across the country. In the regions of higher seismicity (for example the western province and the volcanic region) additional measures are advised. These guidelines will inform policy and are intended to have a systemic impact on housing across Rwanda influencing the construction of safer, durable, comfortable and more resilient buildings, with lower costs and lower carbon footprint than traditional brick homes.

SOIL TESTING

Laboratory and field soil testing was performed to understand if soil testing could be used to determine suitable adobe block making soil.

Soil Testing Methodology

Soils were selected to be representative of common types of soil used for making adobe blocks in Rwanda. The six soils are both commonly used and yet distinct from each other. They are referred to as Gasabo, Rwamagana, Musanze, Nyarugenge, Kicukiro and Kamonyi.

To determine the properties of the soils, particle size distribution and Atterberg limits were measured in laboratories and a number of field tests were performed.

Particle size distribution

An extensive review of existing literature around earth construction demonstrated that there is a large range of particle size distributions that allow for suitable blocks. These are presented in Table 1. It should be recognized that these sources may use different formal definitions for the particle sizes; however, for this purpose they can be compared.

Table 1: Literature recommended particle size distribution for earth construction

Gravel %	Sand %	Silt %	Clay %	Source
	30-75	10-30	10-40	(White, 2013)
35	30	-	35	(Dabaieh, 2014)
	-		40	(Berge, Butters, & Henley, 2009)
	55-70	15-25	10-20	(SENCICO, 2017).
35-70		10-30	10-40	(Walker, 2001)
	-		5-29	(Houben & Guillaud, 1994)
	70-80	10-15		(Brown & Clifton, 1978)
	-		25-45	(Boudreau, 1971)
15-20	45-55	10-20	10-20	(Sri Lanka Standard, 2006)
15	50	15	20	(Centre of Resilience Development, 2012)
0-10	50-80	10-40	5-18	(Indian Standards, 2013)

The following statements can be drawn from the published information in Table 1.

- The maximum recommended clay content is 45%, with most sources recommending a maximum between 20 and 40%.
- The minimum recommended clay content is 5%, but more typically 10%.
- A wide range of total fine content (i.e. silt and clay) is likely to be suitable, varying between 20 and 70%.
- The recommended range of total granular contents (i.e. sand and gravel) varies between 30 and 90%, but is typically around 50%.

The particle size distribution was determined via wet sieve analysis and hydrometer testing, performed by ACTS Rwanda Ltd in accordance with ASTM D422, D1140 and ASTM D7928.

Atterberg limits

Literature provides guidance on Atterberg limits and soil plasticity for earth block making. Some key points are:

- The liquid limit for unstabilized soils should be between 25% and 50% (30%-35% preferred) and the plastic limit between 10% and 25% (12%-22% preferred). Plasticity Index should be 16-33%, (Houben & Guillaud, 1994).
- Indian Standards (2013) recommends a liquid limit < 30%.
- Sri Lanka Standard (2006) recommends a Plasticity Index of 2.5-10.

The Liquid Limit, Plastic Limit, Plasticity Index were measured by ACTS Rwanda Ltd in accordance with ASTM D4318.

Field Tests

The soil field tests in Table 2 and Table 3 were performed to understand if they could be used to predict the adobe block performance.

Table 2: Field soil tests for plasticity, cohesion and clay content

Test	Short description of test	Observations
Ball drop test	A ball of soil barely wet enough to form into a ball is dropped 1.5m onto a flat hard surface. If the ball flattens out with few cracks then it has a high binding force due to a high clay content. If it breaks into many pieces and doesn't resemble a ball then it has a very low binding force. Adapted from (Minke, 2006)	The difference in cohesion between the soils could be identified but not easily measured.
Snake test	The soil is moistened and rolled into a thread on a smooth surface. The thinner and longer the thread without breaking, the higher the plasticity and the clay content.	The "snake" length and diameter could easily be measured and compared between soils. Adobe blocks could not be made from soils that could not be made into a "snake".
Hand Wash test	The soil is moistened and rubbed into the hands. If the soil particles are easily brushed off then there is a low clay content, but if the soil particles require water to remove them then there is a high clay content. Adapted from (Minke, 2006)	It is difficult to describe how challenging it is to remove soil from hands.
Hitting test	Damp soil is shaped into a pat in the hand and hit from the bottom of your hand quickly and repeatedly. If water rises to the top of the soil sample then it has a high silt content.	All water rose to the top somewhat but even though most soils were not classified as silty. Between the soils tested, it was not easy to differentiate between results.
Pat test	Damp soil is shaped into a pat in the hand and pressed flat into the palm. The hand is turned upside down for 20 seconds. If the soil pat does not fall, then it has high cohesion.	The time taken for the pat to fall can be measured.

Table 3: Field soil tests for particle size distribution

Test	Short description of test	Observations
Bottle shaking test	Water is added to soil with a volume ratio of at least 2:1 and in some cases 25mg of sodium chloride is added for every 10g of soil. The ingredients are shaken vigorously in a container and left to settle for 24 hours. The largest particles settle to the bottom and the smallest particles settle on the top, allowing the particle size distribution to be observed and potentially measured. Adapted from (Minke, 2006) and (Sridharan & Prakash, 2000)	The addition of salt decreased settling time; however, it was still a long process. Visually differentiating between soil particle sizes is rarely possible and attempts to measure particle size distribution led to very different results compared to the laboratory tests. Glass and plastic containers were tested since plastic containers are readily available in rural areas however the glass containers did provide more distinct results.
Wash test	Dry soil and record dry weight, vigorously mix water and soil in a bucket and leave for a minute until coarse particles have settled. Carefully pour out the suspended fine particles, add water again and repeat the process until clean water with no suspended fines is observed. Dry the coarse particles at the bottom of the bucket and measure the dry weight to determine percentage of coarse materials.	This test allows the percentage of coarse and fine particles to be determined but cannot provide more detailed particle distribution. The test is simple to perform but takes a couple of days. Soils with a high percentage of fines take longer and are subject to less accurate results. The higher the percentage of coarse material the closer the results were to the laboratory tests.

Conclusions from the soil field testing are presented in the Discussion section of this paper.

Soil Test Results

Soil Classification

The average results from the soil particle size distribution and the atterberg limits are presented in Table 4. These were used to classify the soil using the Unified Soil Classification System (USCS).

Table 4: Soil laboratory test results and classification

Soil name and classification	Average Particle Size Distribution (%)				Average Atterberg Limits (%)		
	Clay	Silt	Sand	Gravel	LL	PL	PI
Typical range of literature recommended results	10 - 40	10 - 50	50 - 70	15 - 20	30 - 35	12 - 22	8 - 16
Kamonyi, Clayey Sand (SC)	15	20	62	4	29	17	12
Nyarugenge, Lean Clay (CL)	28	24	35	14	34	20	14
Gasabo, plastic Silt (ML)	17	42	21	20	46	31	15
Kicukiro, Lean Clay (CL)	24	35	41	0	27	15	12
Rwamagana, Lean Clay (CL)	34	17	49	0	29	18	11
Musanze, non-plastic Silt (ML)	12	75	12	0	n/a	n/a	n/a

LL: Liquid limit. PL: Plastic Limit. PI: Plasticity Index.

These results were used to predict the performance of blocks which is explored further in the Discussion section of this paper.

BLOCK TESTING

The purpose of the block testing was to understand the strength and durability of adobe blocks made from the six representative soils, how varying the fibre content and manufacturing method affected these qualities, and whether field tests could reliably determine strength and durability.

Block Test Methodology

The adobe blocks were subject to up to five types depending on the hypothesis being explored. The compressive strength and drop tests are considered indicators of block strength and the water erosion and abrasion tests are considered indicators of durability. The visual test directly measures block cracking, which is expected to indicate strength and durability.

Visual inspection

Cracking should be limited, so the blocks are able to be handled without damage, structural integrity is not compromised and long term durability is provided.

The visual inspection for blocks was performed in accordance with ASTM E2392. It states that at the end of the curing period blocks should not have developed any crack:

- Longer than 75mm
- Wider than 3mm (major crack)
- Deeper (irrespective of length or width) than 10mm

In addition to the above assessment, the total length of minor (<3mm wide) and major (>3mm wide) cracks has also been measured because it was found to provide a better description of block cracking, rather than a pass or fail result. Table 5 presents photographs of blocks that passed and failed the visual inspection and the length of minor and major cracks.

Table 5: Phase 1 Blocks made from Kamonyi soil illustrating the extent of cracking

Photo of most cracked side of block	
Blocks that pass the ASTM E2392 visual test	Blocks that failed the ASTM E2392 visual test
0mm of major cracks 0mm of minor cracks 	
0mm of major cracks 50mm of minor cracks 	
0mm of major cracks 120mm of minor cracks 	

Compressive strength

Compressive strength of masonry is an important material property for structural applications. It determines the resistance of the block to loading and is used to calculate the characteristic strength which is used in structural design. The blocks were tested in accordance with BS EN 772-1. Blocks were capped with mortar prior to testing to ensure an even load distribution.

Drop test

The drop test in accordance with NZS 4298:1998+A1 was performed to compare against the compressive strength tests and as a measure of corner impact strength which Minke (2006) suggests is more important than compressive or bending strength. A photograph and diagram of the drop test being performed can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Diagram of drop test (left), photograph of drop test (right)

Water erosion

Moisture is one of the biggest risks to unstabilised adobe blocks, therefore a water erosion test was conducted in accordance with NZS 4298:1998 + A1. This test is representative of erosion but not the behaviour of blocks subjected to heavy rainfall, a leaking pipe or flooding. Figure 2 shows a diagram and photograph of the water erosion tests performed.

Figure 2: Diagram of the water erosion test (left), photograph of water erosion test (right)

Abrasion

This test is to determine the abrasive resistance of earth blocks used in facing masonry. The blocks are brushed with a weighted wire brush and the difference in block weight is measured. This is in accordance with Compressed Earth Block Testing Procedures, 2000. Figure 3 shows a diagram and photograph of the abrasion tests performed.

Figure 3: Diagram of the abrasion test (left), photograph of abrasion test (right)

Block Test Phases

Testing was conducted in phases to allow observations from each phase to inform the subsequent phases:

- Phase 1: Manufacture of blocks as they are typically currently made and without fibres to understand the baseline block characteristics.
- Phase 2: Manufacture of blocks as they are typically currently made with the addition of fibres.
- Phase 3: Manufacture of blocks with the addition of fibres and manufacturing methods recommended in literature

There were many variables that could have been tested, however the aim of the two published documents is to improve low income adobe housing, therefore it was not relevant to test variables that would increase cost significantly, such as stabilisers.

Figure 4 shows the timeline for testing and the corresponding seasons. The environmental conditions played a large role in the conclusions from the research as presented in the discussion section.

Figure 4: Testing timeline with weather seasons in brackets

Phase 1 creates a baseline for the block characteristics by testing blocks as they are traditionally made, but with no added fibres, so they can be compared against the blocks from Phase 2 and 3. This traditional method of block production was established through discussions with several experienced masons across the country. It also allows the soils to be compared against each other and in relation to their soil classifications. The laboratory block testing from this phase was also compared to the block field tests to understand if they could represent adobe block performance.

While making blocks for Phase 1 it became clear that Musanze soil alone could not be made into adobe blocks. After discussions with masons local to that area, the Musanze soil was mixed with Kicukiro soil using a 2:1 volume ratio. Throughout the block testing section of this paper the soil is referred to as Musanze-Kicukiro mix.

Phase 2 of testing explored the effect of fibres in block making. According to NZS 4298 '*Straw is generally added to an adobe mix to help control cracking and help the uniformity with which adobe dries*'. Therefore, we hypothesise that fibres will reduce the block cracking. There is some evidence that fibres decrease the strength of blocks (Minke, 2006) although it is often perceived by local masons that fibres increase strength, so this was investigated.

A nation-wide survey was conducted with 84 masons to determine the most commonly used fibres. 87% of the masons typically use fibres, of which 69% say it is to reduce cracking and 31% say it is to increase strength. As seen in Figure 5 there are two main fibre types used in most of the country, Urwiri and Ishinge (photographs in Figure 6).

The masons who do not use fibres are from Ruhango, Rusizi, Nyabihu, Musanze, Burera and Nyamasheke. The masons reported that they did not use fibres said it was for the following reasons:

- Nature of their soil in the district. Their soil has a balance of fines and gravel/sand particles or masons use a combination of soils to reduce cracking.
- Termites. Fibres attract termites which can destroy the wall in the future.
- Use of blocks with small dimensions. Masons from volcanic districts such as Musanze use blocks of small dimensions e.g. 250x150x100mm, which leads to smaller cracks.

Figure 5: Fibre types commonly used

Figure 6: Photographs of Urwiri and Ishinge fibres

The effect of fibre type, quantity and length on block performance were investigated, considering the recommendations in Table 6.

Table 6: Fibre recommendations in literature

Fibre recommendations	Literature
Between 40 and 60mm long Between 5kg/m ³ and 30kg/m ³	HB 195 The Australian Earth Building Handbook
Lengths not exceeding half the finished wall thickness, so 100mm for a 200mm thick wall (typically).	NZS 4298:1998 A1

Phase 3 involved adjustments to the block-making process based on recommendations from literature, to determine the extent to which they improve block strength and durability. This phase compares the "traditional" method (Phase 1) against the "improved" method. An "improved" method has been developed based on a wide range of literature and is presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Phase 3 variables for the improve manufacturing method and their expected outcomes

Variable	Description	Expected outcome
Improved mixing	Soil soaking for 24 hours to improve water distribution through the clay. After it has been left to rest, water may be added and thoroughly and evenly mixed into a workable slurry.	Improved strength due to increased clay cohesion and more consistent properties throughout the block.
Curing	Covering blocks with polythene tarp for 2 weeks to allow slow drying. Curing upright, on a bed of sand.	The slow curing is expected to reduce thermal shrinkage cracks that occur. The bed of sand is expected to protect the base from surface water.
Block size	Two different block sizes will be made: 400x200x200mm & 200x150x100mm. The traditional size is 295x195x145mm.	The bigger size is expected to increase major shrinkage cracks and the smaller size is expected to decrease major shrinkage cracks.

Block Test Results

This section provides the most relevant results that contribute to the Discussion section and respond to the hypothesis.

Block Cracking

Table 8 shows that fibres improved the visual test pass rate and there was no significant difference in cracking between short and long fibres.

Table 8: Phase 2C percentage of blocks that pass the visual inspection test

% of blocks passing visual test	Control blocks without fibres	5kg/m ³ Long Ishinge Fibres	5kg/m ³ Short Ishinge Fibres
Kamonyi	5%	85%	70%
Gasabo	100%	100%	100%
Rwamagana	0%	75%	75%

As shown in Table 9, on the whole, Ishinge fibres reduced major cracks in blocks more so than Urwiri fibres and there was no difference between 5kg/m³ or 10kg/m³ of Ishinge fibres. Either 15kg/m³ or 20kg/m³ of Urwiri fibres was optimal depending on the soil. The results in Table 8 and Table 9 demonstrate cracking in blocks made from Gasabo soil is not reduced when fibres are added.

Table 9: Phase 2A percentage of blocks that have major cracks

Soil type	Total length of major cracks (mm)	Urwiri fibre density				Ishinge fibre density	
		5kg/m ³	10kg/m ³	15kg/m ³	20kg/m ³	5kg/m ³	10kg/m ³
Kamonyi	0	88%	40%	88%	100%	100%	100%
	>0	12%	60%	12%	0%	0%	0%
Rwamagana	0	13%	0%	0%	38%	60%	60%
	>0	87%	100%	100%	62%	40%	40%
Gasabo	0	100%	80%	86%	88%	100%	100%
	>0	0%	20%	14%	12%	0%	0%

The team noticed that the environmental conditions caused by the seasons impacted the drying speed and had a bigger effect on cracking than whether fibres were added to blocks. This was true for blocks that dried too quickly in the sun and cracked, and blocks that dried too slowly and cracked because they were too weak in the drying process. This information was not measured because environmental conditions were not an experimental variable but is reported here nonetheless.

A trend was anecdotally identified that deeper cracks caused the failure of blocks in the drop test along the deep crack line. This was never formally measured.

Block Strength

During Phase 1 35 blocks were crushed to measure compressive strength and 30 blocks were used in the drop test, the results of which are presented in Figure 7 and Figure 8 respectively. There is a higher level of variation from the drop test compared to the compressive strength test. The characteristic compressive strength, calculated using the methodology in NZS 4297, is compared to the average size of the corner piece broken off in the drop test in Figure 9. The coefficient of determination, R^2 , is 0.53, indicating a strong correlation.

Figure 7: Phase 1 block compressive strength for different soils

Figure 8: Phase 1 drop test largest corner break off for different soils

Figure 9: Phase 1 relationship between drop tests and characteristic compressive strength

Table 10 presents the Phase 1 drop test results and the characteristic compressive strength. All soils except the Musanze-Kicukiro mix produce blocks that have acceptable compressive strength, considering that the NZS suggests the minimum design strength to be used is 0.5MPa if no testing is performed, however some blocks still fail the drop test, suggesting that the NZS requirements need to allow for some failures. The NZS considers blocks acceptable if two blocks pass the drop tests, however the high level of variation shown in Figure 8 indicates that a larger number of blocks need to be tested with an allowance for some failures.

Table 10: Phase 1 drop test results for different soils against characteristic compressive strength

Soil type	Average largest piece broken off (mm)	% passing drop test	Characteristic compressive strength (N/mm ²)
Kamonyi	50	100%	2.2
Kicukiro	91	90%	1.6
Rwamagana	115	80%	1.6
Nyarugenge	78	90%	1.5
Gasabo	160	40%	0.8
Musanze- Kicukiro mix	139	50%	0.3

Improved manufacturing in Phase 3 did not impact the strength of the blocks, however the addition of fibre in Phase 2 significantly improved how the blocks behaved in the drop test.

Table 11 shows that both long and short fibres improved the drop test results for Kamonyi and Rwamagana soils, however the same cannot be reported for Gasabo soil, however it was the mason's experience that the fibres meant blocks made from Gasabo soil were more likely to break into two halves rather than shatter, but this is still recorded as a failure in the drop test. The difference between the drop test results in Table 10 and the blocks with no fibres in Table 11 is expected to be due to uncontrolled variables, primarily the weather.

Table 11: Phase 2 effect of adding fibres and their length on drop test results

	Gasabo			Kamonyi			Rwamagana		
	No fibres	Long fibres	Short fibres	No fibres	Long fibres	Short fibres	No fibres	Long fibres	Short fibres
Average largest piece broken off (mm)	208	180	224	160	74	69	170	90	101
% passing drop test	5%	5%	0%	35%	90%	80%	5%	85%	75%

Block Durability

Block durability as measured in the water erosion and abrasion tests was not influenced by the addition of fibres or improved manufacturing methodology.

The results from Phase 3 are not considered reliable due to the heavy rains which impeded the drying process of the blocks but this led to findings regarding block durability during the drying process, which are presented in the Discussion section.

1. Protecting the blocks from rain was most effectively done with a plastic sheet. Banana leaves did not provide adequate protection during heavy rains. Protecting the blocks from surface water could primarily be done with site drainage management but lifting the blocks off the ground was very beneficial. Placing the blocks on a sand layer, as recommended in literature, in fact held surface water rather than allowing it to drain freely.
2. Allowing adequate airflow was only challenging when the blocks had to be protected from rain and neither the plastic sheet or the banana leaves allowed drying to continue while they were in contact with the blocks. The only practical option when the blocks are not protected

by a roof is to support a plastic sheet above them. Unfortunately plastic sheets are relatively expensive and it would have been beneficial to find a cost effective alternative.

DISCUSSION

This section demonstrates how the results and analysis from the soil and block testing have been used to inform the published documents.

Soil testing

It was hypothesised that the performance of adobe blocks could be determined by the soil characteristics. Table 12 presents each of the soils, their expected performance of adobe blocks based on classification, particle size distribution and Atterberg limits and the compressive strength as measured in Phase 1. It is concluded that the combination of particle size distribution and Atterberg limits can predict the performance of adobe blocks. There are several limitations to this conclusion:

1. Only six soil types have been tested and only one of those could not be made into adobe blocks
2. Compressive strength is not the only performance criteria for adobe blocks but it is very important when considering overall block performance
3. The expected performance could only be described in broad terms of good, adequate and poor.

Table 12: Soil expected performance and characteristic block strength

Soil name and classification	Expected performance of adobe blocks based on classification, particle size distribution and Atterberg limits. This was recorded prior to block testing.	Characteristic compressive strength Phase 1 (N/mm ²)
Kamonyi, Clayey Sand (SC)	The particle size distribution is within the recommended ranges for all particle sizes except the percentage of gravel is less than recommended. Atterberg limits are close or within recommended ranges. This soil is expected to produce good adobe blocks.	2.2
Nyarugenge, Lean Clay (CL)	The particle size distribution is close or within the recommended ranges for all particle sizes except the percentage of sand is less than recommended. Atterberg limits are within recommended ranges. This soil is expected to produce good adobe blocks.	1.6
Gasabo, plastic Silt (ML)	The particle size distribution is within the recommended ranges for all particle sizes except the percentage of sand is less than recommended. The liquid and plastic limit are higher than recommended. The soil is expected to produce poorer adobe blocks than other soils.	0.8
Kicukiro, Lean Clay (CL)	The particle size distribution is within the recommended ranges for all particle sizes except the percentage of sand and gravel is less than recommended. Atterberg limits are close or within recommended ranges. This soil is expected to produce acceptable adobe blocks.	1.5
Rwamagana, Lean Clay (CL)	The particle size distribution is close or within the recommended ranges for all particle sizes except the percentage of gravel is less than recommended. Atterberg limits are close or within recommended ranges. This soil is expected to produce acceptable adobe blocks.	1.6
Musanze only, non-plastic Silt (ML)	This soil has a very high silt content and a very low granular content. It is not plastic and is expected to make very weak blocks.	Blocks could not be made from Musanze soil alone

The field tests were performed to understand if they could be used to predict the adobe block performance and therefore whether the soil would be suitable for making adobe blocks. It is concluded that masons can use the field tests to:

1. compare different soils they had performed the test on
2. estimate if adobe blocks could or could not be made from that type of soil
3. broadly understand whether the soil has a high clay, silt or granular content

It was not possible to correlate the results from the field tests and the laboratory tests.

From these conclusions the following was included in the published documents:

1. Broad particle size distribution ranges (granular 30-80%, silt 10-30% and clay 10-40%) were provided for guidance but soil testing is not required if blocks made from the soil pass the block tests
2. Two soil field tests were recommended to help determine the suitability of making adobe blocks:
 - a. the snake test, which allowed clay content to be broadly understood and whether blocks could even be made from the soil
 - b. the soil wash test, which allows granular content to be measured with reasonable accuracy.
3. Local knowledge from experienced trained masons should be sought

Block Cracking

There is an acceptance that blocks crack but controlling wall cracking is more critical:

Whilst the presence of shrinkage cracks in individual bricks may sometimes be a feature of adobe construction, there is a need to limit cracks in completed walls to an acceptable size. (NZS 4297)

Considering this and to reduce the wastage for low income home builders, the published documents allow 10% of blocks that fail the visual crack test to be used in the wall, but they must still be able to be handled.

The ASTM E2392 visual test has been interpreted so that any width crack over 75mm long is a fail, however minor cracks were shown not to have any correlation with strength or durability. Therefore the language in the published documents stated that the cracks had to be “wider than 3mm and longer than 75mm or, irrespective of the crack length or width, deeper than 10mm”.

It was demonstrated that different soils had different optimal fibre content and the fibre content varied between fibre types. Therefore the published documents recommend creating test blocks with varying amounts of fibre and performing the visual and drop test on them to determine the optimum fibre content.

Block Strength

The drop test has been modified from the NZS and included in the published document. The modified version requires a minimum of 20 blocks to be tested rather than two and a pass rate of 80% indicates good performance. These modifications account for the high level of variability observed in the drop test. The size of the corner piece that can break off in the test has been increased to 150mm from 100mm because it was found that the linear relationship between compressive strength and the drop test results (Figure 9) demonstrated that a corner piece of 150mm breaking off still met the minimum compressive strength requirements.

A minimum compressive strength of 0.5MPa is stated in the standard but it is considered to be achieved if the drop test is successful, which is possible due to the strong correlation between compressive strength and drop test results (Figure 9).

Block Durability

As expected, adobe block durability was not improved through the addition of fibres or adjustment of manufacturing method. Therefore the recommendations in the published documents rely on three methods of protection:

1. adequate roof overhangs to limit contact with rain directly and rain splash back
2. elevating the wall off the ground on a non-permeable material to limit contact with moisture from the ground and rain splash back
3. a sacrificial layer of mud plaster that protects the walls from direct water and abrasion. The mud plaster layer needs to be maintained.

The water erosion and abrasion tests were not included in the standard because they should not influence the protection measures used.

Soil chemical stabilisation is well known to improve durability, however it was not a variable tested as part of this research project because it was not considered a financially viable solution for the majority of adobe home builders in Rwanda. Nonetheless it was mentioned as an option for improving durability in the published documents.

Environmental Conditions

While all efforts were made to control the unknown variables it was not possible to isolate the project from the effects of the weather. It was observed that the weather had a significant impact on the performance of the blocks and even whether the blocks could be dried. The published documents emphasise the importance of controlling the drying process by:

1. Protecting the blocks for rain and surface water.
2. Allowing adequate airflow around the blocks so drying can continue.
3. Shading from direct sunlight to avoid rapid drying, which is expected to lead to cracking. Shading from direct sunlight was not a tested variable in this project and shading is not typically practised; however, during this project the blocks were well shaded either to protect them from rain or by the open sided shed the manufacturing facility was in. This would have been a valuable variable to have tested.

Control blocks were made during Phase 2 and 3 to compare the experimental blocks against, however the quantity was limited.

The effects of climate change are being felt in Rwanda with less predictable seasons and more intense rainfall. The impact this will have on adobe construction practices and the adobe homes themselves is not understood.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.